

complexes show two weak bands at 485 and 640 nm due to the transitions ${}^1T_{2g} \leftarrow {}^1A_{1g}$ and ${}^1T_{1g} \leftarrow {}^1A_{1g}$ respectively.

In the ir spectra of the ligands, a band observed at 3200 cm^{-1} due to $\nu_{\text{N-H}}$ is absent in the spectra of the complexes. So the NH moiety was deprotonated due to complex formation. The $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ band observed at $\sim 1680\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the ligand remained unaltered in the complexes suggesting that oxygen is not taking part in the complex formation. The spectra of the complexes show two new bands due to $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ and $\nu_{\text{C-S}}$ at 1610 and 690 cm^{-1} respectively. This new $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ band and the change of $\nu_{\text{C-S}}$ of the ligand to $\nu_{\text{C-S}}$ in the complexes suggest that the complex formation occurred through the sulphur atom. Probably the complex formation occurred through a tautomeric change:

as the ir frequency changes demand. $\nu_{\text{M-N}}$ and $\nu_{\text{M-S}}$ bands are observed at 550 and 380 cm^{-1} .

The values of g_{\parallel} (2.14–2.2) and g_{\perp} (2.08–2.09) were calculated from the anisotropic spectra which are typical of monomeric Cu^{II} complexes. $g_{\parallel} > g_{\perp}$ suggests an elongated tetragonal geometry and the unpaired electron in the $d_{x^2-y^2}$ orbital⁷.

Nmr spectra of the n-butyl derivative (Co^{III}) shows a triplet at $\delta 1.7$ for the methyl group. The two middle CH_2 signals are complex and are centred at $\delta 2.0$ and 2.3 . The CH_2 group attached to the nitrogen atom of the quinazolone ring is deshielded giving a triplet at $\delta 4.8$. Signals due to the aromatic protons are observed at $\delta 7.6$ – 8.3 . The aromatic proton at position-5 is deshielded by the bromine atom and the carbonyl oxygen; hence the extreme signal at $\delta 8.3$ is considered to be due to this proton. The allyl derivative shows a signal due to CH_3 at $\delta 1.8$. The quartet due to CH adjacent to the CH_3 group is observed at $\delta 5.4$. The other CH group shows a resonance at $\delta 6.0$ because the nucleus is deshielded by nitrogen. The aromatic proton signals are observed at $\delta 7.8$ – 8.5 . In addition to the aromatic proton signals, the n-propyl derivative shows signals at $\delta 1.75$ (t, CH_3) signal (complicated) due to $-\text{CH}_2-$ at $\delta 2.2$ (CH_2) and 4.7 (t, CH_2 attached the nitrogen atom). The signal due to NH is always difficult to identify because of the quadrupole moment of nitrogen and the exchange of this proton. However, a peak observed at $\delta 3.2$ in the ligand is absent in the spectrum of the complexes and is assigned to NH proton. Its absence in the complex shows that the coordination to Co^{III} has taken place through nitrogen atom.

Thus in Cu^{II} , Ni^{II} and Co^{III} complexes of 6-bromo-3-alkyl-4-oxoquinazoline-2-thiones the four-membered ring formed on complexation is quite

stable. X-Ray study of stable four-membered ring including metal ion, similar to the complexes studied here has been reported by Cartwright *et al.*⁸. The stability of the complexes may be due to the π -backbonding to the vacant d -orbitals of sulphur atom.

It has been observed that the substitution of an electronegative atom in the aromatic ring of quinazolones has some effect on the stereochemistry of their complexes. Irrespective of the fact that the substituent at nitrogen-3 is alkyl or aryl and even having no substitution, it has been found that these benzene-substituted-thioquinazolones do not form Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} aquo-complexes as in the case of 3-N-alkylthioquinazolones. The Ni^{II} complexes formed in this case are tetrahedral. The Co^{III} complexes of the benzene-substituted-thioquinazolones do not contain trapped water molecules in the interstitial spacing as in case of the corresponding complexes of the unsubstituted ligands.

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Metal Complexes as Ligand. Binuclear Alkali Metal Complexes with Nickel Ethylenediamine Oxalate and Cobalt Ethylenediamine Oxalate

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NICKEL(II) and cobalt(II) ethylenediamine (en), oxalates (Ox), $[\text{Ni/Co}(\text{Ox})\text{en}]$ have been used as 'metal complex ligands' in the synthesis of oxygen-bridged polynuclear alkali metal complexes of the general formula $[\text{M}_b\text{L}\{\text{M}_a(\text{Ox})\text{en}\}]$, where $\text{M}_a = \text{Ni}^{\text{II}}$ and Co^{II} ; $\text{M}_b = \text{Li}$, Na and K; and L = deprotonated 1-nitroso-2-naphthol (1N2N). The

NOTES

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL, PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	Colour	Decomp. temp. °C	$\nu_{C=O}$ cm ⁻¹	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			μ_{eff} B.M.
				Ni/Co	N	K/Na	
Ni(Ox)en≡X	Violet blue	260	1 620	—	—	—	3.28
Li1N2N.X	Brownish yellow	198	—	14.6 (15.0)	10.4 (10.8)	—	3.51
Na1N2N.X	Brownish yellow	205	1 615	14.1 (14.4)	10.2 (10.4)	5.5 (5.7)	3.50
K1N2N.X	Brownish yellow	195	1 610	18.2 (18.8)	9.40 (10.1)	9.0 (9.3)	3.40
Co(Ox)en≡Y	Light orange	250	1 625	—	—	—	5.20
Li1N2N.Y	Deep brown	220	1 600	14.8 (15.2)	9.8 (10.7)	—	4.80
Na1N2N.Y	Brownish black	215	1 620	14.0 (14.6)	9.9 (10.4)	5.4 (5.7)	4.80
K1N2N.Y	Deep brown	208	1 610	18.6 (14.1)	9.2 (10.0)	9.1 (9.3)	4.80

*At 300 K.

magnetic moment, electronic and infrared spectral studies indicate that the polymeric octahedral 'metal complex ligands' change to tetrahedral monomers in the adducts.

Experimental

The usual method of the synthesis was to take metal ethylenediamine oxalate $[M(\text{Ox})\text{en}]^0$ in absolute ethanol and alkali metal salts of 1N2N were added to it in 1 : 1 molar ratio. The mixture was refluxed on hot-plate for 3–4 h with constant stirring, and the resulting adducts were precipitated in hot condition.

The colours of the adducts $[M_a(\text{Ox}(\text{en}(M_bL))]$ were different from those of $[M_a(\text{Ox})\text{en}]$. The decomposition temperature of the adducts were also different from those of their parent complexes. The compounds were stable under anhydrous condition but decomposed on exposure to moisture. Elemental analysis, characteristic ir bands and magnetic moment (300 K) data are presented in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

The existence of nickel ethylenediamine oxalate complexes $[\text{Ni}_2\text{en}(\text{Ox})^0]$, $[\text{Ni}(\text{en})_2(\text{Ox})^{2-}]$ and $[\text{Ni}(\text{en})\text{Ox}]^0$ in solution have been reported^{2,3}. The nature of the anion was found to be a contributing factor towards the stability of these complexes.

In $[\text{Ni}/\text{Co}(\text{Ox})\text{en}]^0$, the $\nu_{C=O}$ bands occurred at 1 620–1 625 cm⁻¹ (i.e., lower than 1 650 cm⁻¹)^{1,4}, suggesting a bridged oxalate structure; the free and terminal C=O groups of oxalate show $\nu_{C=O} > 1 700$ cm⁻¹.

For the alkali metal adducts, the $\nu_{C=O}$ of the oxalates have been observed always below 1 650 cm⁻¹. This suggests that the oxalate groups are not free or terminal ones in the alkali metal adducts,

but most likely bridged. In all these adducts the ν_{NH} occurred at 3 200–3 300 cm⁻¹. The CH₂ rocking vibrations again show up as a single peak at 790–830 cm⁻¹. The adducts show three bands at 485–600 cm⁻¹ which are very conclusive for a *trans*-structure of all these alkali metal adducts bridging two Ni/Co ions, which is in conformity with the observations of other workers⁵.

The visible absorption spectrum of Ni(Ox)en shows typical Ni^{II} octahedral spectra with three absorptions at 370, 580 and 925 nm. In the alkali metal adduct $[\text{Na1N2N.Ni}(\text{Ox})\text{en}]$, there has been one absorption at 620 nm, suggesting a tetrahedral structure for Ni^{II} ion. The Co(Ox)en complex shows only one band at 475 nm. In its alkali metal adducts, there has been only one peak at 510 nm. Thus the octahedral structure of Co/Ni in these 'complex-ligand' suggests a change to tetrahedral one in these alkali metal adducts.

The values of magnetic moment of Ni(Ox)en is 3.28 B.M., and that for its alkali metal adducts 3.42–3.52 B.M. The magnetic moment of Co(Ox)en is 5.20 B.M. The alkali metal adducts with Co(Ox)en have magnetic moments of 4.80 B.M. So there has been a change in the stereochemistry of Ni^{II} and Co^{II} in the 'complex-ligands'; both are octahedral while in the alkali metal adducts, both showed tetrahedral structures.

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